

**A Study on the Accuracy of the Computerized Radiographic
Measurement of the Femoral Head Size**

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Introduction

With the advent of new technology Digital X-ray systems are now widely used in hospitals nationally and internationally. Most systems have facilities to take measurements from the images. Which can be used in accurate pre-operative planning. Insertion of undersized head is a cause of increased joint loading of the acetabulum and may result in acetabular erosion. Inappropriate implant size could affect the outcome of the surgery with reported complications such as stress shielding, loosening, micro motion, dislocation, acetabular erosion. Despite the use of larger head sizes dislocation continues to be the most common mode of failure leading to revision. Due to the importance of arthroplasty for the success of hip joint replacement, this study is aimed to analyze the difference in conventional radiographic method, digital radiograph and actual measurement of the femoral head. Conventional method of measurement is from the X-ray film measuring the widest diameter of the femoral head subtracting 10% and preparing implant sizes +_5.

This study could be used as a tool for the radiographic and actual femoral head size assessment by decision making clinical practice pre-operatively. This study may reliably predict the size of the implant required for hemiarthroplasty to treat hip fractures.

GENERAL OBJECTIVE

To evaluate the accuracy of the computerized radiographic size of the femoral head who underwent partial hip arthroplasty.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES:

To measure the femoral head size using computerized radiographic system.

To measure the actual femoral head size intra-operatively.

To determine the difference between the CR measured femoral head size and the actual size of the dissected head between pre op femoral head size and the actual size of the diseased head.

Due to the importance of arthroplasty for the success of hip joint replacement, this study is aimed to analyze the difference in conventional radiographic method, digital radiograph and actual measurement of the femoral head.

This study will be useful in assessing difference in radiographic and actual size assisting in decision making

during clinical practice.

Study Design

Descriptive Analysis

Materials and Methods

Pre operative pelvic Xray AP and cross table lateral views were taken upon admission. All patients admitted at NMMC for hemiarthroplasty from January 2013 were included in the study. Computerized Radiographic measurements were taken preoperatively.

Intraoperative

The diameters of femoral heads in 24 Hip joints were measured using a caliper at the head equator. Intra-operative measurements were noted and recorded as shown in the figures below.

Fig 1.Measurement shown in the right femoral head Fig1.1 Measurement using Traumacad Fig 2.1-2.3 showing intraop measurements using head sizer and fig 2.6vernier caliper

Results

In this study there were 17Females and 7 males with a mean age of 70 years old who underwent Partial hip Arthroplasty from January 2013 to November 2014. Eight patients had intertrochanteric fractures while other17 patients sustained femoral neck fractures.

Patient	Age/Sex	Diagnosis	Computerized Radiographic Size	Actual Size measured By Caliper	Difference In Measurement
Px.A	74/F	FX Closed Intertrochanteric (L)	46mm	44mm	2 mm
Px.B	54/F	Untreated Femoral Neck FX(L)	52mm	50mm	2 mm
Px.L	65/M	FX Closed Intertrochanteric Femur (L)	50mm	49mm	1 mm
Px.M	80/M	FX Closed Femoral Neck (R)	45mm	43mm	2 mm
Px.T	82/M	FX Closed Intertrochanteric Femur (L)	48mm	47mm	1 mm

Px.R	77/F	FX Closed Intertrochanteric Femur (L)	47mm	46mm	1 mm
Px.B	70/F	FX Closed Intertrochanteric Femur (L)	46mm	46mm	0 mm
Px.B	80/F	Femoral Neck FX (L)	44mm	44mm	0 mm
Px.R	75/F	FX Closed Intertrochanteric Femur (L)	54mm	54mm	0 mm
Px.F	55/F	FX Closed Intertrochanteric Femur (L)	42mm	42mm	0 mm
Px.C	71/F	FX Closed Intertrochanteric Femur (L)	46mm	44mm	2 mm
Px.V	71/F	FX Closed Femoral Neck (L)	42mm	42mm	0 mm
Px.D	87/F	FX Closed Intertrochanteric Femur (R)	46mm	44mm	2 mm
Px.D	76/M	FX Closed Intertrochanteric Femur (L)	45mm	45mm	0 mm
Px.C	53/F	FX Closed Femoral Neck (R)	43mm	44mm	1mm
Px.E	65/M	FX Closed Femoral Neck (R)	50mm	49mm	1mm
Px.R	62/F	FX Closed Intertrochanteric (R)	43mm	43mm	0mm
Px.S	71/F	FX Closed Femoral Neck (L)	44mm	44mm	0mm
Px.S	65/M	FX Closed Femoral Neck (L)	50mm	49mm	1mm
Px.W	56/F	FX Closed Femoral Neck (L)	44mm	44mm	0mm
Px.Y	70/F	FX Closed Femoral Neck (L)	46mm	46mm	0mm
Px.S	52/F	FX Closed Femoral Neck (L)	42mm	42mm	0mm
Px.O	61/M	FX Closed Femoral Neck (R)	49mm	48mm	1mm
Px.D	72/F	FX Closed Femoral Neck (R)	44mm	42mm	2mm

Table 1.0 Measurement of femoral head by different modalities

Preoperatively using the computerized method of measurement of the femoral head of each patient was measured. Double set up Radiographic size -10 % ; plus or minus 51 mm, different sizes ranging from the values taken were prepared. Five patients had the same radiographic size with the actual femoral head size. Eleven patients had a difference value of 1mm with the radiographic size.

[Chart Placeholder: Comparison Bar Graph of Radiographic vs Caliper Measurements]

The table above presents the mean radiographic measurement (46.0833mm) with Standard deviation 3.374 and the mean actual measurement (45.2916mm) with Standard deviation 3.182 of the patients (n=24). It can be seen that there is only a mean difference of 0.7 mm between the measurements taken by the two modalities. Statistically this study showed that 80% of the patient's radiographic size is 1mm higher with what of the actual femoral head size.

Statistical Breakdown Table

NO. OF PX	Computerized Measurement	Caliper Measurement
1	46	44
2	52	50
3	50	49
4	45	43
5	48	47
6	47	46
7	46	46
8	44	44
9	54	54
10	42	42
11	46	44
12	42	42
13	46	44
14	45	45
15	43	44
16	50	49
17	43	43
18	44	44
19	50	49
20	44	44
21	46	46
22	42	42
23	49	48
24	44	42
Average	46.08333333	45.29166667
Standard Deviation	3.374026067	3.182549794

The computed standard deviation is 3.37 and 3.18 on both measurements meaning that the values in the data set are close to the mean – noting that the measured sizes prepared were close to the values (radiographic size minus 1 or 2 mm) of the exact intra operative size as shown at table.

It can then be said that there is no significant difference between the measurements taken radiographically and intra-operatively.

However, comparing the computerized and traditional method of measurement our study shows that preoperative planning with computerized radiographic system estimates the nearest size of the implant with a mean difference of 0.79 mm which clearly signifies that computerized radiographic measurement is more reliable than conventional methods.

Conclusion

In this preliminary report of 24 patients who underwent partial hip Arthroplasty, it was noted that using computerized radiographic system the size measured pre operatively and actual femoral head size measured intraoperatively is almost the same with the mean difference of 0.88mm..With traditional system we need to prepare a stock the full range of hemiarthroplasty implants. Sizes at the extremes of the ranges needed to be prepared for single surgery .Our study measurement.-operative planning using computerized radiograph estimates the nearest size of the implants needed to be prepared which would ease many orthopedic surgeons from storing sizes of implant at extremes on the shelf a huge advantage of computerized radiography over conventional radiograph and some factors like distance of the beam to plate will vary according to the radiographer's positioning of the xray source if these things are standardized our study shows that hip prosthesis size can be accurately predicted from pre-operative images using computerized measurement.